

Management of a Closed Complete Long Oblique Fracture of the Mid Humeral Diaphysis in 1-Year-Old Domestic Short Hair Tom Cat: A Case Report

Ahmad, U.S.^{1*}, Shehu, S.A.², Bodinga, A.H.¹ & Aminu, A¹

¹Department of Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Nigeria

²Department of Veterinary Anatomy, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria

Received 30 May, 2025, Accepted 5 June, 2025, Published 30 June 2025

A 1-year-old male Domestic Short Hair cat weighing 3 kg was presented to the Small Animal Unit, Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, with acute non-weight-bearing lameness following an outdoor excursion. The cat was fed milk, fish, and table scraps, with no prior history of medication or vaccination. On physical examination, the patient was alert and active but avoided bearing weight on the left forelimb. Palpation of the brachium revealed swelling and crepitation. The mucous membranes were pink, and capillary refill time was less than two seconds. Vital parameters were within normal limits, except for mild bradycardia and tachypnea. Hematological analysis revealed values within normal ranges, with a mild monocytosis. Radiographic evaluation confirmed a closed, complete, long oblique fracture of the mid-humeral diaphysis. Surgical stabilization was performed using standard orthopedic techniques. Postoperative management included analgesia, antibiotics, and restricted activity. The patient demonstrated progressive improvement in gait, appetite, and wound healing over successive follow-ups. The fracture site remained stable without complications. Sutures were removed two weeks postoperatively. The lack of owner compliance resulted in the patient being lost to subsequent follow-ups. As such, the long-term clinical outcome and the efficacy of the reduction procedure could not be formally documented.

Keywords: Cat; Humeral fracture; Orthopaedic surgery; Postoperative care; Fracture stabilization; intramedullary pinning

INTRODUCTION

Humeral fractures are among the least common long bone fractures in small animals. Their relatively low incidence, combined with the complex anatomy of the humerus, makes their repair particularly challenging (Amelia, 2004). Midshaft humeral fractures are especially difficult to manage due to the bone's unique morphology, the close proximity of the radial, median, and ulnar nerves and their associated vessels, and the relative rarity with which these fractures are encountered in clinical practice. The humeral diaphysis is particularly prone to developing oblique fracture configurations, which are inherently unstable when subjected to axial loading and torsional

stress (Gall *et al.*, 2022). Surgical stabilization is therefore often indicated for long oblique fractures to minimize the risk of displacement, malunion, and subsequent limb dysfunction (Peirone *et al.*, 2002; Langley-Hobbs, 1997).

Open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) of humeral shaft fractures can be performed successfully via either a lateral or medial surgical approach. For the lateral approach, exposure of the midshaft humerus is typically achieved through a craniolateral incision. During this procedure, meticulous care is required to identify and protect the radial nerve, particularly in the distal portion of the incision.

Intramedullary (IM) pinning, either as a sole technique or in combination with adjunctive fixation methods such as cerclage wiring or tie-in configurations with external fixators, remains a widely accepted approach for Ahm

*Corresponding author's e-mail: umar.ahmad@udusok.edu.ng.

Table 1: Ranges of normal vital parameters

Rectal Temperature (°C)	Pulse rate (beats/min)	Respiratory rate (cycles/min)
37.8 – 39.2	110 – 130	20 – 30

(Hassan and Hassan, 2003).

Table 2: Hematological findings

Parameters	Obtained values	Reference values
PCV (%)	36.94	30.00 – 45.00
Hb (g/dl)	12.3	9.80 – 15.40
RBC ($\times 10^6$ cells/mm ³)	9.50	5.00 – 10.00
WBC ($\times 10^3$ cells/mm ³)	16.29	5.50 – 19.50
Neutrophils ($\times 10^3$ cells/mm ³)	11.73	2.50 – 12.50
Lymphocytes ($\times 10^3$ cells/mm ³)	2.17	1.50 – 7.00
Monocytes ($\times 10^3$ cells/mm ³)	*1.43	0.00 – 0.90
Basophils ($\times 10^3$ cells/mm ³)	0	0.00 – 0.10
Eosinophils ($\times 10^3$ cells/mm ³)	*0.95	0.00 – 0.80
Band cells	0	0

Key* Indicates abnormal value

stabilizing midshaft humeral fractures in feline patients. This method is favored for its relative simplicity, biomechanical stability, and minimal disruption of surrounding soft tissues (Altunatmaz *et al.*, 2012; Yeh *et al.*, 2021). Intramedullary pin placement may be carried out using either a normograde or retrograde technique, depending on surgeon preference and fracture configuration (Tomlinson 2003; Montavon *et al.*, 2009).

The purpose of this report is to describe the clinical and radiographic examination of humeral fracture in a cat as well as successful reduction of the fracture using a combination of Cerclage wires and intramedullary pinning.

CASE HISTORY

A one-year-old male Domestic Short Hair cat weighing 3.0 kg was presented to the Small Animal Unit of the Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The client reported that the cat had suddenly developed lameness and was unable to bear weight on the left forelimb after returning home from an outdoor excursion the previous day. The cat was fed milk, fish, and table leftovers, with no prior history of vaccination or medication (Plate 1).

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

On physical examination, the patient appeared active and alert, although it was immediately evident that it was not bearing weight on the left forelimb. Palpation revealed swelling and crepitation over the left humeral region, suggesting a possible fracture. General clinical examination showed the following vital parameters: rectal

temperature, 39.9 °C; pulse rate, 92 beats per minute; and respiratory rate, 68 cycles per minute. The mucous membranes were pink, with a capillary refill time of less than two seconds (Table 1).

Hematological evaluation revealed values within normal limits: packed cell volume (PCV) 36.84%, hemoglobin (Hb) 12.03 g/dL, total white blood cell count (WBC) 16.29×10^3 cells/mm³, and red blood cell count (RBC) 9.50×10^6 cells/mm³. However, monocytic leukocytosis (1.43×10^3 cells/mm³) was observed, indicative of an inflammatory response or tissue injury (Table 2).

Radiographic examination confirmed a closed, complete, long oblique fracture of the mid-humeral diaphysis. Based on these findings, a diagnosis of a closed complete long oblique fracture of the mid-humeral diaphysis was established.

SURGICAL MANAGEMENT

Pre-surgical evaluation revealed that all vital parameters were within normal limits: rectal temperature, 38.7 °C; pulse rate, 120 beats per minute; respiratory rate, 32 cycles per minute; mucous membranes were pink with a capillary refill time of less than two seconds; and packed cell volume (PCV) was 36.94%.

The patient was placed on 0.9% normal saline administered intravenously. Premedication was achieved using 2% xylazine hydrochloride at 1 mg/kg IV for sedation, followed by 5% ketamine hydrochloride IV to induce general anesthesia.

The surgical site was shaved and aseptically prepared using Purit® antiseptic (chlorhexidine gluconate B.P. 0.3% w/v, cetrimide B.P. 3% w/v; Sero Lifecare Ltd., Lagos, Nigeria). The area was scrubbed, rinsed with

Plate 1: The Radiograph showing the Lateral view of the Left forelimb

Plate 2: Showing the Patient after draping and scrubbing

Plate 3: Showing the Exposure of the Fractured bone

Plate 4: Showing the Surgical wire after application

Plate 5: Closure of the skin and application of povidone iodine solution

Plate 6: Post-surgical Radiograph showing complete reduction and placement of IM pin

methylated spirit (Binji Global Pharmaceutical Co., Sokoto, Nigeria), and painted with povidone-iodine (Iodine Tincture 2.6% w/v solution; Apacco Pharmaceutical Co. Ltd., Ogun, Nigeria). The surgical field was draped using the triangular draping technique (Plate 2).

A 5–6 cm straight longitudinal skin incision was made along the lateral aspect of the humerus, extending approximately 2 cm above the lateral epicondyle distally (Plate 3). The deltoideus, triceps brachii, and brachialis muscles were bluntly dissected and retracted to expose the lateral surface of the humeral diaphysis (Piermattei and Johnson, 2004). Examination revealed a closed, complete, long oblique fracture of the mid-humeral diaphysis with minimal soft tissue trauma.

Fracture fragments were anatomically reduced and stabilized using an intramedullary stainless-steel pin (IMPIN®) inserted in a retrograde manner into the medullary cavity, complemented with cerclage wire fixation. Proper reduction and alignment were confirmed visually and by ensuring limb symmetry before closure (4).

The muscle and subcutaneous layers were sutured using size 3/0 chromic catgut in a simple continuous pattern, while the skin was closed with size 3/0 vicryl in a simple interrupted pattern (plate 5).

Postoperative management included Piroxicam 1% at 0.3 mg/kg intramuscularly for five days for analgesia; Pronor® (benzyl penicillin sodium B.P. 1,000,000 IU [600 mg] and procaine penicillin B.P. 3,000,000 IU [3 g]) administered intramuscularly at 20,000 IU/kg for five days; Streptomycin sulfate 5 g at 12.5 mg/kg intramuscularly for five days; Vitamin B12 (0.5%) at 150 µg intramuscularly for five days; and 10% povidone-iodine applied topically for wound dressing (plate 5). Postoperative radiograph revealed correct reduction and fragments alignments, and stable implant positions (6).

DISCUSSION

This case highlights the practicality and effectiveness of intramedullary (IM) pin and cerclage wire fixation for managing simple midshaft humeral fractures in feline patients. Previous studies have reported favorable healing outcomes with IM pinning when appropriate case selection and meticulous surgical technique are applied (Altunatmaz *et al.*, 2012; Cohen *et al.*, 2012). In cases requiring additional stability such as comminuted fractures a tie-in configuration that combines an intramedullary pin with an external skeletal fixator can provide superior mechanical support and predictable healing outcomes (Peirone *et al.*, 2002; Langley-Hobbs, 1997).

Recent retrospective analyses and multicase series further support these fixation strategies, demonstrating satisfactory outcomes in feline humeral fractures (Gall *et*

al., 2022; Yeh *et al.*, 2021). Factors that contribute to successful recovery in fracture patient likely included timely surgical intervention, precise anatomical reduction, appropriate pin sizing and placement, and diligent postoperative management encompassing analgesia, infection control, and restricted activity (Mathews *et al.*, 2014; Hudson *et al.*, 2020).

A thorough understanding of the safe corridors for pin insertion and potential complications such as articular cartilage damage associated with retrograde distal pinning is critical. Anatomical studies have cautioned against certain retrograde techniques that may endanger periarticular structures (Cohen *et al.*, 2012; Prackova *et al.*, 2022). Overall, this case contributes to the growing body of clinical evidence supporting intramedullary pin fixation complemented by cerclage wiring as a practical and effective alternative for midshaft humeral fractures in cats, particularly in settings where implant availability or financial constraints limit the use of plating systems.

CONCLUSION

Regardless of the patient lost to follow-up due to poor owner compliance, which precluded a comprehensive evaluation of the long-term clinical outcome and the efficacy of the fracture reduction, it will be concluded that the surgical treatment of midshaft humeral fractures in cat with cerclage wire and intramedullary nailing is a safe technique to improve fracture reduction. The use of cerclage wires leads to better bone contact while minimizing malunions.

REFERENCES

- Altunatmaz, K., Özsoy, S., Mutlu, Z., Devcioglu, Y., & Guzel, O. (2012). Use of intramedullary fully threaded pins in the fixation of feline and canine humeral, femoral and tibial fractures. *Vet. and Comparative Orthopaedics and Traumatol.*, 25(4), 321–325. <https://doi.org/10.3415/VCOT-11-05-0068>
- Amelia M. Simpson. (2004). Fractures of the humerus. , 19(3), 0–127 doi:10.1053/j.ctsap.2004.09.004
- Cohen, L., Israeli, I., Levi, S., Benzioni, H., & Milgram, J. (2012). Normograde and retrograde pinning of the distal fragment in feline humeral fractures. *Vet. Surg.* 41(5), 604–610. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1532-950X.2012.00999.x>
- Gall, N., Parsons, K., Radke, H., Comerford, E., Mielke, B., Grierson, J., Ryan, J., Addison, E., Logethelou, V., Blaszyk, A., & Langley Hobbs, S. J. (2022). Analysis of feline humeral fracture morphology and a comparison of fracture repair stabilisation methods: 101 cases (2009–2020). *J. Feline Med. and Surg.*, 24(6), e19–e27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098612X221080600>
- Hudson, C. C., Kim, S. E., & Pozzi, A. (2020). Percutaneous pinning for fracture repair in dogs and cats. *Veterinary Clinics of North America: Small Animal Clinical Practice*, 50(1), 101–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cvsm.2019.09.001>
- Langley Hobbs, S. J. (1997). External skeletal fixation for stabilisation of comminuted feline humeral fractures. *Veterinary and Comparative Orthopaedics and Traumatology*, 10(3), 157–164. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9239628/>
- Mathews, K. A., Kronen, P. W., Lascelles, D., Nolan, A., Robertson, S., Steagall, P. V., & Wright, B. (2014). Guidelines for recognition,

- assessment, and treatment of pain in animals. *Journal of Small Animal Practice*, 55(6), E10–E68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsap.12200>
- Peirone, B., Camuzzini, D., Filippi, D., & Valazza, A. (2002). Femoral and humeral fracture treatment with an intramedullary pin/external fixator “tie-in” configuration in growing dogs and cats. *Veterinary and Comparative Orthopaedics and Traumatology*, 15(2), 85–91. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0038-1632719>
- Piermattei DL, Johnson KA: Approach to the midshaft of the humerus through a craniolateral incision, in Piermattei DL, Johnson KA (eds): An atlas of surgical approaches to the bones and joints of the dog and cat (ed 4). Philadelphia, WB Saunders, 2004, pp 156-159
- Prackova, I., Paral, V., & Kyllar, M. (2022). Safe corridors for external skeletal fixator pin placement in feline long bones. *Journal of Feline Medicine and Surgery*, 24(10), 1008–1016. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098612X211057329>
- Tomlinson JL: Fractures of the humerus, in Slatter D (ed): Textbook of small animal surgery (ed 3). Philadelphia, WB Saunders, 2003, pp 1905-1918
- Yeh, S. D., Wong, A., & Smith, P. (2021). Description of outcomes after tie-in and reinforced external skeletal fixation for feline humeral fractures: 46 cases (2010–2019). *Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association*, 259(5), 510–516. <https://doi.org/10.2460/javma.259.5.510>